

Complementary information about the poster:

Effortless Counting of Sorted *Culicoides* from Light Traps

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1. THE *IMAGEJ* MACRO TO COUNT *CULICOIDES* SPECIMENS

The macro used in the ImageJ software is as follows:

```
1. //Macro ImageJ pour compter des Culicoides sur une assiette blanche
2. // dans un lit d'alcool 70.
3. // les Culicoides sont triés d'un piege lumineux et propres
4. run("Gaussian Blur...", "sigma=2");
5. run("Median...", "radius=2");
6. run("Subtract Background...", "rolling=50 light create");
7. //setTool("freehand");
8. title = "DELINEATE THE COUNTING AREA";
9. msg = "Delimitez la zone de comptage puis faites OK.";
10. waitForUser(title, msg);
11. run("Find Maxima...", "prominence=2 light output=Count" );
12. nombre = (getResult("Count"));
13. run("Clear Results");
14. if (nombre > 2000) {
15. prom = 1.5;
16. } else {
17. prom = 2;
18. }
19. run("Find Maxima...", "prominence=&prom light output=Count");
20. run("Find Maxima...", "prominence=&prom light output=[Point Selection]");
```

A *Culicoides* specimen preserved in alcohol and captured in a photograph, displays pixels that vary in shades of black. The head and thorax, in particular, appear darker than the rest of the

body. However, other regions, such as the wings or abdomen (especially in parous females) can also appear darker. However, in nearly all cases, a *Culicoides* specimen can be represented by a cluster of pixels, within which a distinct peak can be identified on a dark-to-light scale.

The Macro is based on the FIND MAXIMA command (lines 10 and 11), a tool used to identify and highlight local maxima (peaks) within an image. This process is commonly applied in tasks such as detecting bright spots in microscopy images or identifying features like particles or cells. For optimal performance, certain parameters in the “Find Maxima” process must be carefully configured, such as the 'prominence,' also known as 'Noise Tolerance.' This value determines how distinct a peak must be compared to the surrounding pixels to qualify as a maximum. Higher values detect more prominent maxima, while lower values allow for the detection of subtler maxima.

The blurring process (steps 4, 5, 6) is designed to generate, for each *Culicoides* specimen, a distinct mass of pixels with a peak value. These steps also introduce a form of standardization across photographs, ensuring that the prominent value for the 'find maxima' process remains consistent. In the final step, the counting area must be carefully delineated to minimize the inclusion of artifact pixels.

Details of the steps are as follow:

- **Steps initiating with** // are comments (steps 1, 2, 3, 7).
- **Step 4: Gaussian blur.** The sequence of commands is PROCESS > FILTER > GAUSSIAN BLUR with parameter Sigma (radius) = 2.00. In ImageJ, the **Gaussian Blur** process is a common image filtering technique used to reduce noise and detail in an image. It works by applying a Gaussian function, which is essentially a bell-shaped curve, to smooth the image. This operation blurs the image by averaging the pixel values within a given radius, with closer pixels having more influence than those farther away, according to the Gaussian distribution. Gaussian blur is commonly used in pre-processing steps to standardize images before performing tasks like feature detection (e.g., maxima detection) or object counting in noisy or detailed images.
- **Step 5: Median Filter.** The sequence of commands is PROCESS > FILTER > MEDIAN with parameter Radius = 2.00. In ImageJ, the Median Filter is a non-linear image processing filter used primarily to reduce noise while preserving the edges of objects in an image. It works by replacing each pixel's value with the median value of the neighboring pixels within a specified radius, rather than the average as in linear filters. The median filter is particularly effective at removing **salt-and-pepper noise** (random black-and-white noise) from images while maintaining sharp transitions between regions of different intensities. Unlike a Gaussian or average filter, it better preserves edges, as it doesn't blur them significantly.
- **Step 6. Subtract Background.** The sequence of commands is PROCESS > SUBTRACT BACKGROUND with parameter Rolling ball radius = 50 pixels and “Light background” checked (as our photographs are on a light background). The "Subtract Background" function is commonly used for removing uneven illumination or background noise from images, particularly in biological or scientific imaging. This is important when you're

trying to enhance the contrast between the object of interest and the background for more accurate analysis. The “**Rolling ball radius**” is an important parameter. It determines the size of the structures considered as background. The radius is typically set based on the size of the objects under study. Larger radii remove larger background features, while smaller radii remove finer background noise.

- **Steps 8, 9, and 10** involve user interaction. The ImageJ program will wait until the zone of interest (where the *Culicoides* are located in the photograph) is correctly delineated. The use of the 'Freehand' selection tool is recommended.

- **Step 19 and 20. Find Maxima.** Is the search for maxima with the “Light background” option has been checked.
 - **Step 19** will show the counts (numbers of peaks counted)
 - **Step 20** will mark the recognized peaks with a dot on the photograph.

The prominence value to be used in steps 19 and 20 is computed (as “prom”) in steps 11 to 18.

- **Step 11** uses the "Find Maxima" process with a prominence value of 2.
- If the number of peaks (referred to as "nombre" and obtained in Step 12 as 'Counts') is greater than 2000, the prominence value (prom) is set to 1.5 and passed to Steps 19 and 20. (*Note: Step 13 hides the result table of this preliminary estimation of the number of peaks.*)
- If the number of peaks is less than 2000, the prominence value (prom) remains 2.

This variation in the prominence value is due to the fact that when the value is set to 2, it works well for counts of *Culicoides* below 2000 in the plate. However, when the count exceeds 2000, the automatic detection may slightly overestimate the count by approximately 20-30 individuals. However, despite this overestimation when prominence value remains 2, the results remain within an acceptable range, but with the prominence correction (at 1.5), counts were almost correct.

2. SOME RECOMMENDATIONS.

The use of ImageJ with our macro is powerful; below are some recommendations:

1. Use a white background when taking photographs (a white plate is convenient)

2. Ensure the *Culicoides* specimens are submerged in sufficient alcohol volume, approximately a few millimeters deep.
3. Avoid the presence of artifacts, such as other insects or debris of any kind.
4. Avoid bubbles on the surface of the alcohol.
5. Do not overcrowd the sample. *Culicoides* should not be stacked on top of each other. In case of a large number of *Culicoides*, please divide the sample into several smaller batches. A density of 1500 -2000 insects on a 20 cm diameter (bottom) plate is appropriate. If batches of very numerous culicoides is to be counted, it is convenient to divide the batch into several smaller batches of appropriate density.

3. MEASUREMENT OF AGREEMENT BETWEEN STEREOMICROSCOPIC COUNTING AND IMAGEJ COUNTING

The comparison between counting with a stereomicroscope and with the ImageJ software was carried out using two approaches to provide complementary insights into the two measurement techniques: The Bland-Altman analysis and the Passing-Bablok regression.

- **The Bland-Altman analysis** is a method used to assess the agreement between two different measurement techniques. It is particularly useful for evaluating the agreement between a new method and a standard or reference method. It focuses on the agreement between two methods by analyzing the differences, helping to identify bias and variability. The Bland-Altman Analysis generates a plot showing differences versus means, along with limits of agreement, helping visualize how much the two methods differ. The key components of this analysis include:
 - **Plotting Differences:** The differences between the two measurement methods (Method A - Method B) are plotted against their mean.
 - **Limits of Agreement:** The analysis calculates the mean difference and the limits of agreement, which are typically set at ± 1.96 standard deviations from the mean difference. This helps to visualize how much the measurements differ on average and the range within which most differences lie.
 - **Assessment of Bias:** It allows for the identification of any systematic bias (consistent overestimation or underestimation) between the two methods

The Passing-Bablok regression is a non-parametric method used for assessing the relationship between two measurement methods, particularly when the data does not meet the assumptions of traditional regression analysis (e.g., normality). The method provides a statistical framework to quantify the relationship and compare the results between methods through regression analysis. It aimed at quantifying the relationship between two methods, providing information about proportionality and constant bias through regression analysis. Produces a regression equation (slope and intercept), indicating how one method relates to the other in terms of linearity. It indicates whether one method consistently overestimates or underestimates compared to the other and quantifies the nature of the relationship. Key aspects include:

- **Robustness:** It is robust against outliers and does not require the assumption of a normal distribution.
- **Slope and Intercept:** This method calculates the slope and intercept of the relationship between the two methods, providing insights into proportional differences and constant bias.
- **Comparison:** It helps determine whether the two methods yield equivalent results or if one systematically overestimates or underestimates the other.

The Bland -Altman analysis was carried out with the R package “blandr” using the two commands “bland.output.text” and blandr.draw (for the graph). Reference: Datta D. 2024. “blandr”: Bland-Altman Mathod Comparison. CRAN

The Passing-Bablok analysis was carried out using the R package “mcr” (function “mcreg” for parameters computation, and “plot” for the graph). Reference: Potapov S., Model F. Schuetzenmeister A.,Manuilova E., Dufey F., Raymaekers J. 2024. Package “mcr”: Method Comparison Regression. CRAN.

4. PRELIMINARY RESULTS (AS PRESENTED IN THE POSTER)

The analysis of *Culicoides* counting involved 91 pairs of counts (stereomicroscope vs. ImageJ counting), ranging from 10 to 2220 specimens. Photographs for ImageJ counting were taken with a Samsung S9 cell phone, positioning the (white) plates (20cm diameter at the bottom) and containing *Culicoides* in alcohol at approximately 30 cm away. Resolution of photographs was 3024 x 3024 pixels (9,1 megapixels) on the cell phone.

Preliminary results of Bland-Altman analysis were the following:

Number of comparisons: 91
 Maximum value for average measures: 2215
 Minimum value for average measures: 10
 Maximum value for difference in measures: 25
 Minimum value for difference in measures: -17

Bias: -2.395604
 Standard deviation of bias: 6.795226

Standard error of bias: 0.7123332
 Standard error for limits of agreement: 1.221827

Bias: -2.395604
 Bias- upper 95% CI: -0.9804302
 Bias- lower 95% CI: -3.810779

Upper limit of agreement: 10.92304
 Upper LOA- upper 95% CI: 13.35041
 Upper LOA- lower 95% CI: 8.495665

Lower limit of agreement: -15.71425
Lower LOA- upper 95% CI: -13.28687
Lower LOA- lower 95% CI: -18.14162

Derived measures:

Mean of differences/means: -2.549688
Point estimate of bias as proportion of lowest average: -23.95604
Point estimate of bias as proportion of highest average -0.1081537
Spread of data between lower and upper LoAs: 26.63728
Bias as proportion of LoA spread: -8.993426

Bias:
-2.395604 (-3.810779 to -0.9804302)
ULoA:
10.92304 (8.495665 to 13.35041)
LLOA:
-15.71425 (-18.14162 to -13.28687)

The bias and its 95% confidence interval are represented by the blue band in the graph. The bias is nearly zero, with a slight overestimation observed in the automatic counting by ImageJ.

However, most data points fall within the agreement zone, which is delineated by the red and green lines representing the lower and upper limits of agreement, respectively, both with their corresponding 95% confidence intervals. There is just one outlier, but the discrepancies is minimal (about 25 from 1750 counted *Culicoides*, which remains in an acceptable practical range).

Preliminary results of the Passing-Bablok regression were the following:

	EST	SE	LCI	UCI
Intercept	0.90	NA	-0.2002564	1.950192
Slope	1.01	NA	1.0009909	1.025000

The representation of the regression line is (method 1 is stereomicroscope counting, method 2 is the automatic ImageJ counting):

The 0.95-confidence bounds are calculated with the bootstrap(quantile) method.

The regression analysis indicates that the two methods are in good agreement, with a slight overestimation by ImageJ when the counts are high, as previously noted in the Bland-Altman plot. However, the discrepancies are minimal and remain well within an acceptable range.
